

An investigation into the spatial heterogeneity of MIMO device with 3D deterministic channel modelling using single-probe anechoic chamber method

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Abstract—The multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) over-the-air (OTA) testing technique is envisaged capable of effectively emulating the channel environment. While characterizing classical cellular channels, spatial correlation can be used to evaluate the differences correlation between each pair of transmit and receive antennas. In the next-generation wireless systems, the presence of reflectors close to the wireless device in a complex electromagnetic environment as well as toward higher carrier frequency will cause heterogeneous channel characteristics. Consequently, the current MIMO OTA emulation techniques represented by multi-probe anechoic chamber (MPAC) method will hardly emulated the heterogeneity channels by planewave-based architecture. We propose a single-probe anechoic chamber (SPAC) based MIMO OTA solution to emulate the heterogeneous deterministic channel, which has been decomposed and synthesized for each array element in a temporally sequential manner. Both the theoretical analysis and simulation results demonstrate the proposed method can effectively extend the application scenarios for SPAC based MIMO OTA emulation.

Index Terms—MIMO OTA testing, heterogeneous channel, spatial correlation, channel modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) over-the-air (OTA) testing technique has been widely utilized for factory performance testing of MIMO devices, which is usually referred to as Devices Under Test (DUT). The test results can provide a valid indication of the realistic performance of the MIMO device. It is generally believed that the utilization of MIMO OTA technology can effectively benefit multiple stages in both the R&D and field deployment of wireless devices. The efficient implementation of MIMO OTA testing relies on the ability to efficiently reconstruct and emulate various channel models in a laboratory environment.

Ideally, a MIMO OTA testing system is envisaged to emulate the real-world propagation scenarios the DUT experienced by generating the correspondent electromagnetic field surrounding the DUT inside the test zone. Nevertheless, there is challenge in its implementation over cost and equipment complexity. The current state-of-the-art solution is

the Multiple-probe anechoic chamber (MPAC) method, which choose to emulate geometry-based statistical wireless channel model as a simplified target. In the MPAC method, multiple probes deployed around the DUT have been employed to simultaneously transmit plane waves to emulate both impulse responses and spatial correlations using the spatial position in the test zone. As a result, different array elements of DUT will observe a copy of given channel impulse response attenuated with spatial correlation coefficients [1].

The most MIMO system relies on efficient spatial multiplexing to support the independent multiple data streams. Although this independence is essentially caused by surrounding environments of which the MIMO devices deployed, the study of the channel transfer function in [2] indicates that the spatial correlation can be utilized as a statistical tools to describe the coupling effect of multiple independent data streams. This is particularly true for the outdoor cellular systems. In this scenario, each array element of the MIMO system will face almost the same channel impulse responses due to the limited number of nearby reflectors and the compact spacing between array elements. Then, the spatial correlation refers to the phase variation due to the spatial relative position between multiple array elements. These assumptions have been adopted in numerous wireless channel models, e.g., 3GPP Spatial Channel Model Extended (SCME) model [3] and clustered delay line (CDL) model [4]. Consequently, almost all MIMO OTA testing standards, e.g., 3GPP TR827 [5] and CTIA [6] utilize the spatial correlation as the most important validation metric.

However, along with the evolution of wireless technologies, MIMO systems have been utilized in much wider scenarios including smart manufacturing, in vehicle communication, and numerous indoor Internet of Things (IoT) systems. In these scenarios, the MIMO devices will be surrounded by massive reflector surfaces, which will generate complex electromagnetic environments. Not surprisingly, different antenna elements of the DUT will now observe essentially homogeneous channel responses, as shown in Fig. 1(b). It should

be aware that the carrier frequency has been significantly increased along with the evolution of wireless systems, while the city environment is also becoming complex along with the urbanization. As a result, the plane wave assumption may no longer be satisfied even in the outdoor cellular channel for the next generation wireless systems. In other words, the differences between individual channels observed by different array elements cannot be adequately described using spatial correlation alone in the complex electromagnetic environment.

An important key challenge is that the current MIMO OTA testing system represented by MPAC method can only emulate the spatial correlation based channel models. The MPAC method is based on the plane wave synthesis principle with the direction of incidence towards the center of the test zone, which results in a geometrically centered symmetrical response in the test zone for each signal path. Then, one envisages that there will be significant difference between the achievable performance of devices deployed in these scenarios and the indication obtained through MIMO OTA testing system. Consequently, the capability to emulate the 3D heterogeneous deterministic channel model should be one of the most important targets for the next generation MIMO OTA testing system.

In this work, we propose the novel method to support the emulation of 3D heterogeneous deterministic channel model, which is derived from our previous proposed single-probe anechoic chamber (SPAC) method and referred to as SPAC-H method. Unlike the MPAC method only utilizes the spatial synthesization, the SPAC employs an additional Degree of Freedoms (DoFs) through time synthesization. Furthermore, the probe in SPAC method will move to different incident angles and transmits the pre-faded data stream, while a time synthesizer will align and synthesise the multiple streams to reconstruct the fading signal with coupling effects of each array element. The process of synthesising multiple data streams by the time synthesizer enables the SPAC method to regard the antenna system of the DUT as a combination of several individual elements during the channel emulation. Then, the SPAC-H method can further decompose the transmitted pre-faded signal to a signal observed at each receiving array element. Thus, by correcting the spatial correlation at each position, the physically spatial correlation can be replaced by the channel parameters expected at the individual array elements, while preserving the antenna pattern characteristics. As a result, the SPAC-H method is compatible with both the traditional statistical channel models and array-based deterministic channel models, which is capable of making MIMO OTA technology applicable in much wider advanced wireless scenarios, thus benefiting more researchers and developers of wireless community.

The organization of this paper is as follows: Different schemes for different channel scenarios and the corresponding MIMO OTA emulation methods are discussed in Sec. II. In Sec. III, the deterministic heterogeneous channel modelling and improved SPAC methods are investigated. The simulation based experiments will be discussed in Sec. IV.

Fig. 1. The channel characteristics for different channel scenarios.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The MPAC is currently the mainstream MIMO OTA emulation method. With a carefully designed infrastructure and necessary calibrations, numerous probes will emit signals and synthesize the desired spatial electromagnetic field around the DUT. The impulse response observed by r th antenna element of DUT from the k th probe can be expressed as:

$$h_{r1,k} = h_k \cdot \exp(j\beta d_{r1,r0} \vec{r}_k), \quad (1)$$

where h_k is the allocated signal for k th probe, β is $2\pi/\lambda$, λ is the wavelength of center frequency, and \vec{r}_k is the unit vector with direction from k th probe. Similarly, the impulse response of r 2th antenna element can be expressed as:

$$h_{r2,k} = h_{r1,k} \cdot \exp(j\beta d_{r2,r1} \vec{r}_k). \quad (2)$$

The exponential parts in Eqs. 1 and 2 show the effect of spatial correlation, i.e. different antenna elements of DUT will observe the homogeneous channel impulse response with different phases, as shown in the diagram below in Figs. 1(a). As discussed, this assumption is reasonable in the case of outdoor cellular channels, where the signals can be regarded as an approximate plane wave around the receiver after reflection and scattering effects in the propagation path. In other words, the MPAC method is capable of effectively emulating the wireless channels observed by the DUT in an cellular scenario.

However, in the indoor scenarios, especially the industrial environments with complex electromagnetic environments, strong reflections from large equipment and machines make the wireless channel much more complex. In these scenarios, the principle of homogeneous channel model may not be still satisfied. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the observed channel impulse responses in different array elements may emerge essentially different, instead of simple phase differences, i.e., the heterogeneous channel model should be employed to characterize the wireless channels rather than the homogeneous spatial channel models. Therefore, simply using spatial correlation to model the variation of the signal between different elements of the DUT in these scenarios is envisaged difficult to provide an accurate emulation.

The traditional ray-tracing method is an efficient deterministic channel modelling method. In the typical usage of applying

ray-tracing method for MIMO systems, the position of the centre of the multi-antenna system is usually utilized as the reference point for generating the basic impulse response, and the channel parameters of each antenna element superimpose the phase variation due to spatial correlation [7]. Nonetheless, this is intended to ensure compatibility with the well developed spatial channel model. However, if the antenna array of the MIMO devices is considered as a collection of independent elements, the ray based channel modelling process can be calculated for each element individually. Fig. 1(b) shows a typical modelling results of a dual element antenna array. The differences between the two channels are significant even with compact spacing between two array elements. In particular, the few paths with high magnitude of one of the element may considerably affect the actual performance of the wireless device.

It is clear that deterministic modelling based on individual elements can accurately describe the heterogeneity between multiple elements with the aid of ray-tracing method. As discussed above, channel modelling method based on spatial correlation may no longer be capable to characterise the heterogeneity of realistic channels. Consequently existing MIMO OTA testing systems represented by the MPAC method may also have difficulty in emulating the heterogeneous deterministic channels.

III. METHODOLOGY

In a series of our previous work [8], [9], the SPAC based MIMO OTA testing method has been proposed. The SPAC method is able to effectively model spatial characteristics based on spatial correlation within the test zone. In order to further satisfy the individual element-based ray-tracing channel modeling, SPAC method has been extended to the SPAC Heterogeneous (SPAC-H) MIMO OTA method with the ability to model MIMO channels with spatial heterogeneity. The SPAC-H method aims to emulate the individual element-based channel model without affecting the pattern of antenna system of the DUT. This has been done with the aid of the time synthesizer to achieve the ability to have different antennas corresponding to different channel parameters unconstrained with the spatial correlation.

As with the SPAC method, the antenna system of the DUT is placed in the center of the virtual sphere, while each antenna is connected to its own time synthesizer. By activating the channel parameters corresponding to the current array element and its time synthesizer, the single probe will be moved to each of the preset positions in turn and emits a pre-faded data stream at the incident direction, which is then captured by the time synthesizer. After the single probe has visited all incident angles of every element, the time synthesizers will align and synthesize the captured data streams, which will generate the expected fading data stream for individual element. In this process, the basic channel impulse response emulated by the SPAC-H method can be expressed as:

$$h_{n,r}^{OTA} = h_{n,r}^{ray} \cdot \exp(j\beta\Phi_{n,r}(\phi, \theta)), \quad (3)$$

where $h_{n,r}^{OTA}$ is the direct emulated impulse response by SPAC-H method with phase variance of spatial position, $h_{n,r}^{ray}$ is the target channel parameters, which is generated by ray-tracing modeling, and $\Phi_{n,r}(\phi, \theta)$ is the spatial vector caused by current incident angle and spatial position of the n th path of r th element.

As shown in Sec. II, the SPAC-H method has to compensate for the effect of the spatial position embedded in the observed impulse response other than the ray-tracing modeling. A calibration matrix \mathbb{C} is introduced to calibrate for the spatial influence due to the MIMO OTA channel emulation. The element of the calibration matrix \mathbb{C} can be written as:

$$C_{n,r} = \exp(j\beta\vec{r}(\phi_n^{AoA}, \theta_n^{AoA}) \cdot d_r), \quad (4)$$

where d_r is the spatial distance of the r th array element from the geometric centre of the test zone. As a result, the impulse response of the calibrated SPAC-H method can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{h}^{OTA} &= \mathbb{C}^T \cdot h^{OTA}(t, \tau) \\ &= \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{n=1}^{N_r} C_{n,r} \cdot h_{n,r}^{OTA}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

It should note that the emulation process for r th element in Eq. 5 is independent from other elements, as the probe will emit pre-faded signals for each element in sequential manner.

Compared to SPAC method and other channel emulation methods, the proposed SPAC-H method is capable of characterising the more detailed individual element-based ray-tracing channel emulation, which is in trade with the increased measurement time. However, even with the increased measurement time, the proposed SPAC-H method may essentially enhance the capability boundary of MIMO OTA testing system for deterministic channels and benefit the deployment and optimization of wireless networks in these scenarios. In addition, the ability of the SPAC-H method to capture data streams is help to improve and understand the actual performance of wireless devices during the R&D stage.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

In this section, we first show the simulation setup of deterministic channel modeling and SPAC-H solution. The results of the impulse response and the package error rate (PER) of the DUT are presented through SPAC-H channel emulations generated from array-based and heterogeneous deterministic channel models, respectively. Then, the PER results of the SPAC-H system with the position errors are compared. Finally, the simulation results of MPAC method for the array-based channel model are compared with the errors of the SPAC-H method for emulating more realistic and heterogeneous channel scenarios, and the simulation results match the theoretical analysis.

A. Simulation Setup

The deterministic channel modeling scenario using the ray-tracing method is shown in Fig. 2. The transmitter is deployed at the ceiling corner; the DUT of the MIMO OTA emulation, i.e. the receiver, is deployed at two separate types of locations, where Line of Sight (LOS) propagation paths

Fig. 2. Deterministic channel modeling scenarios and modelling results.

are present or not, respectively. Ray-tracing modeling utilizes the SBR method to generate propagation paths; the maximum number of reflections is set to three, since the power of the paths generated by more reflections is considerably low. The antenna system of receiver is deployed in both array-based and individual element-based modes at the same position.

The basic architecture of SPAC-H method remains the same as that of SPAC solution. The test zone is set as a plane with a length and width of 0.25 m, which can satisfy the requirement of the max element spacing of 1λ . Based on the results of the deterministic channel modeling, the single probe moves to the allocated incident angle of every array element in sequence to generate the impulse response in test zone. The synthesised data stream is then transmitted to the DUT for PER calculation. As an important wireless protocol that introduces MIMO technology, the throughput of IEEE 802.11n protocol would cover the requirement of data transmission in industrial scenarios [10]. The high data rate of MIMO systems means that more reliable channel estimation is required, but the difficulty of channel estimation is further increased in harsh electromagnetic environments. Therefore, based on the trade-off between transmission speed and the complexity of the wireless protocol, the IEEE802.11n protocol was used in the simulation for both the transmitter and receiver. In practical SPAC-H method deployments, the single probe may generate a position error during movement between numerous incident angles. This position error is set to be no greater than 2 degrees on the 3D virtual sphere.

B. Experience Results

As described in Sec. II, the MPAC system uses spatial correlation to describe the spatial characteristics of the MIMO system; the SPAC-H system is able to further emulate the spatial heterogeneity of the MIMO devices. Fig. 3 shows the average impulse response emulated by MPAC and SPAC-H OTA system in the test zone, in which the impulse responses generated by the array-based and heterogeneous simulations are quite different. It is important that the impulse response emulated by spatial correlation is symmetrical based on the geometric center point. However, the impulse response of heterogeneous emulation is the superposition of the corresponding different array elements, which makes the overall impulse response not completely symmetrical.

Fig. 4 shows the PER generated by the DUT after channel emulation. The blue and orange lines represent the PER

Fig. 3. Emulated average impulse response in the test zone.

Fig. 4. PER of the DUT after homogeneous and heterogeneous channel emulation.

results for the cases with element spacing of 0.8λ and 1λ , respectively. The channel of solid line is the deterministic heterogeneous channel emulated by the SPAC-H method, while the dashed line corresponds to the deterministic array-based channel emulated by MPAC method. Fig. 4(a) shows a channel scenario where LOS paths are found, while Fig. 4(b) corresponds to an NLOS channel scenario. From the results, one observes clear difference in PER under different channel scenarios. Furthermore, the device performance difference reflected by the SPAC-H method for the two modeled channels at the same physical location also changes with the change of the array element spacing. In other words, when the distance between the array elements is different, the difference of the PER corresponding to the devices passing through the two channels is obviously different. This result further demonstrates that the heterogeneity between multiple elements of MIMO device in indoor scenarios can seriously affect the actual performance of the device and that the SPAC-H method can effectively emulate the characteristics of heterogeneous channels. At the same time, it is shown that MIMO devices are sensitive to the deployment environment in complex electromagnetic environments, where small changes in position can lead to significant changes in performance.

The incident angle error, or probe position error, is the typical error in MIMO OTA emulation. A deviated incident angle will affect the accuracy of the impulse response in the test zone, and therefore the accuracy of the emulation. Fig. 5 illustrates the impact on the performance of the DUT when the MIMO OTA emulation system has position errors. The solid and dashed lines represent the PER of the DUT for the ideal channel emulation and the MIMO OTA emulation with position errors, respectively. The emulation results indicate that the difference in performance of the devices are not

Fig. 5. PER of the DUT for channel emulation with positioning errors.

Fig. 6. Emulation error of the mean impulse response in the measured area.

significant and only slightly different due to position error. This means that the MIMO OTA system can further trade off the positioning device accuracy and deployment costs when deployed in practice.

Finally, the error between the array-based modeled impulse response emulated by the MPAC method and the more realistic heterogeneous deterministic modeled channel emulated by the SPAC-H method is calculated. As shown in Fig. 6, the error between the impulse response emulated by the MPAC method and the ideal heterogeneous channel is significantly larger than the error between the heterogeneous channel emulation and the target impulse response by the SPAC-H method. Statistical errors were calculated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). Statistical errors based on array element spacing of 0.8λ and 1λ are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
RMSE OF SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

Element spacing	0.8λ	1λ
MPAC	0.629	0.059
SPAC-H	0.649	0.0581

Table I illustrates that the MPAC method is difficult to emulate heterogeneous channels directly, while the SPAC-H method is able to emulate the heterogeneity of the different elements.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we improve the SPAC channel emulation method and make it possible to accurately emulate the heterogeneous channels of MIMO devices in complex electromagnetic environments. In harsh electromagnetic environments, spatial correlation is difficult to accurately characterize the heterogeneous channels observed by different elements of MIMO devices. Using the abundant geographical information, the individual element-based deterministic channel modeling method can provide more accurate channel characteristics.

However, this heterogeneous deterministic channel model failed to be successfully emulated by the current MIMO OTA technologies represented by MPAC solution. This paper proposes a novel the SPAC-H method, which is capable of effectively describing heterogeneous channel models and preserving multiple antenna system characteristics in the analog domain. The SPAC-H emulation method extends the application scenarios of MIMO OTA emulations and will benefit multiple stages in both the R&D and field deployment of wireless devices. And we are working to implement the SPAC-H emulation system in the anechoic chamber, the results of which will soon be provided in our following work.

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